

DETECTION OF PLANT LEAVE DISEASE USING HYBRID TECHNIQUES

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Abstract

Plant illnesses are not good for you elements that reduce crop quality and quantity significantly. Biologists or farmers with a lot of experience frequently inspect plants for illness with their naked eyes, however this procedure is typically inaccurate and takes a long time. We apply artificial intelligence and computer vision techniques in this work to create and construct an intelligent classification system for leaf diseases. This study compares the simulation results of two approaches for performance evaluation. In the first section, photos data from Plant Village collection (for apple, maize, Plants for potatoes, tomatoes, and rice) are augmented with data, and deep features are retrieved using a neural network using convolutions (CNN). A Bayesian optimal machine classifier using support vectors is used to classify these characteristics, and the results are measured in terms of precision, sensitivity, f-score, and accuracy. The approaches described above will allow farmers all around the globe to take early action to avoid their crops from becoming irrevocably damaged, so sparing the world and themselves from a possible economic disaster. The second stage of the approach begins with the preparation of data set photos, after which texture and colour characteristics are retrieved using histograms of oriented gradients (HoG), GLCM, and colour moments. In this case, the three categories of features, namely colour, texture, and depth, are merged to generate hybrid features. To get simulation results, binary particle swarm optimization is a technique for reducing the number of particles in a used to pick these hybrid features, followed by classification using a random forest classifier. Binary optimization of particle swarms is a technique for lowering the total number of particles in a technique for lowering the total number of particles in a critical in hybrid feature selection; the reason behind this Algorithm is to provide the best output with the fewest features. The above-mentioned assessment factors are used to conduct a comparative study of both methodologies.

Keywords. Leaves classification, Leaves disease segmentation, Machine learning, Convolution neural networks, Bayesian optical support vector machine classifier, Swarm optimization.

1. INTRODUCTION

The fall in crop quality and quantity has a direct impact. The phrase "pesticides" was established to battle, control, and minimise the impacts of bio-Diseases, pests, and other unpleasant compounds contained in logical creatures and illnesses, and crops can cause a dramatic fall in agricultural productivity [2]. Typically, the recognition of plants pests and diseases [1]. The influence of these harmful elements on crops is often assessed by visual examination based on the leaves' appearance, morphology, and other qualities. This visual inspection should only be conducted and assessed by a highly experienced biologist, as misdiagnosis might result in irreversible yield loss. It should be mentioned that pest and disease management research is often expensive and need the presence of a professional biologist to detect and prevent disease development and transmission as early as feasible [3].

The connection between DL technology and computer vision has resulted in the development of clever algorithms that analyse and categorise patterns or pictures more accurately than the typical person. DL is concerned with machines learning to think using architecture modelled after the nervous system, whereas computer vision is concerned with computers learning to think and act with little human

intervention [4]. In the aftermath of the above, computer technology for the automated Plant disease identification [5] has arisen, and a system for detecting foliar diseases using a smartphone has been developed employing two network architectures, AlexNet [6] and GoogLeNet [7]. The suggested model was educated and obtained 99.35% accuracy in detecting leaf diseases. They employed the R-CNN diagnostic algorithm, which is quicker than CNNs, to detect early- grown corns and separate them from weeds in three distinct climates, yielding an average analytical result of 97.71 percent. Fuentes and colleagues [8] evaluated the three different sorts of sensor families with regard to different architectures and found that the quicker R- CNN combined with the VGG-16 design produced superior results.

"Plant diseases can cause severe harm to agricultural crops by dramatically lowering output [9] because they limit crop development and result in poor product quality [10]." Because of their lower yield and fibre content, biofuel crops are becoming more popular as agriculture struggles to keep up with the world's constantly rising population. With the naked eye, an established approach for detecting and identifying plant leaf diseases is noticed [11]." However, because symptoms are appraised based on individual experiences, this manual identification might lead to misdiagnosis [12]. Plants must also be checked on a frequent basis to prevent disease transmission. This constant monitoring is a tough task since it takes a significant amount of time [13]. As a result of the above, computational strategies for automatic detection have emerged, as demonstrated in [5,] which built a system in order to diagnose plant leaf diseases aided by cellphones. "They employed data that is open to the public collection of 54,306 photos of damaged and healthy leaves, as well as two CNN architectures, AlexNet [6] and GoogLeNet [7]." Their suggested model was educated and achieved 99.35 percent accuracy in detecting leaf diseases. However, when evaluated on sets of photographs shot under diverse settings, it fared badly." Brahimi and colleagues [13] used leaf pictures to train a CNN model to classify tomato illnesses. They employed visualisation approaches to interpret the symptoms and so pinpoint the locations of the leaf sickness in order to examine the deep model. The collected findings were 99.18 percent accurate. Recommended using natural photos of healthy and damaged rice leaves and stems obtained from the experimental field to identify ten prevalent rice illnesses. The method classified cucumbers into two usual illness classifications and one healthy class with an average accuracy of 94.9 percent." However, the aforementioned studies only use a tiny group of designs. The current study offers to compare the performance of pretrained CNNs AlexNet, GoogLeNet, and InceptionV3 [14], Squeeze Net [15], ResNet50, and ResNet101 to see which classifies better and produces results in less time. By encompassing 5 crop species and 19 illnesses, it becomes a full tool for researchers who need to build and apply a mechanism that is sufficiently thorough in the categorization plant leaf diseases that have been exploited in agriculture. Compare the most prevalent imaging methods for object analysis and classification.

2. METHODOLOGY: -

A. Improved Monitoring System for Crop Production : -

The suggested monitoring system for enhancing crop yield monitoring consists of three distinct phases: picture pre-processing, detection, and communication. Various data mining methodologies are created for each phase. Several procedures the first step is dedicated to pre-processing soil and plant photographs. The next stage is undertaking the process of predicting plant disease and its causes because of the soil characteristics. The last stage makes use of the information technology to notify farmers by disseminating the Plant kinds, plant diseases, and their causes in this case, these three distinct phases in the monitoring system are described in section briefly explained.

B. Image Pre-processing Phase: -

Initially, photos of various plants and soil are acquired using a digital camera with the necessary resolution for higher quality. The recorded photos are sent to the image processing unit for further

processing through a wired or wireless network. The acquired pictures are then pre-processed to remove noise and other disruptions from the images and to improve the characteristics for the prediction process. The noise in the images is removed, and the RGB photos are transformed to grayscale into colour space representations. The improved photos are then segmented using a segmentation algorithm based on Region of Interest (ROI). ROI segmentation is a technique for determining the profitability of a business divide a picture into a number of areas or classes. It's written as follows:

$$R_{i \geq j} = \frac{\psi \cdot \frac{|R_i| |R_j|}{|R_i| + |R_j|} \cdot \|u_i - u_j\|^2 + (1 - \psi) \cdot ew}{1(\partial(R_i, R_j))} \quad (1)$$

In equation (1), R_i and R_j signify the two neighbouring areas of the area, (R_i, R_j) is the length of the two regions, refers to the weight of $(0,1)$, e signifies the border strength, and u_i, u_j represent the spectral values of two regions.

The model of a polygonal leaf is used to recover the contour properties of plant pictures. Then, using a dictionary of botanical plant species that contains descriptions of many types of plant species, semantic representation is given to these contour data in order to discover the types of plant.

Then, using texture, colour, and form feature extraction algorithms, the characteristics are recovered from plant photos. The inner-distance is used to extract form characteristics from plant photos, which is then used to generate shape descriptors based on shape contexts. The length of the shortest path between the sight spots within the form border is defined as inner-distance. O is defined as a linked and closed subset of R^2 . The inner the distance between two people points (R_i, R_j) is represented by the letter $d(x_i, x_j; O)$. The context of shape at position h_i also referred to as histogram h_i of a relative the remaining $n-1$ points' coordinates.

$$h_i(k) = \#\{x_j: j \neq i, x_j - x_i \in \text{bin}(k)\} \quad (2)$$

The similarity between the two points is calculated as a weighted combination and is expressed as,

$$D = aD_{ac} + D_{sc} + bD_{be} \quad (3)$$

D_{ac} signifies the appearance difference, D_{be} means the bending energy, and D_{sc} denotes the shape context distance, which is an average distance between two places in the preceding equation (3). Weights a and b are used in this example. The inner-distance is used by the form context to determine the spatial relationship between sight spots. As a result, the inner-angle $(x_i, x_j; O)$ is supplied for the orientation bins. Based on the fractal geometry, the geometric parameters are retrieved. The length N of the geometrical object X may be calculated using the rule with length u . The fractal dimension is then calculated as follows:

$$D_x \propto \lim_{u \rightarrow 0} \frac{\log N}{\log u} \quad (4)$$

C. Plant Disease Prediction: -

The Transudative Support Vector Machine predicts plant disease based on plant type and plant characteristics (TSVM). When compared to a training dataset, TSVM is used to detect the presence of illness in plants. Assume that the training characteristics of plant

pictures are $(x_1, y_2), \dots (x_l, y_l)$, $y \in \{-1, 1\}$ and $x^*_1, \dots x^*_k$ are non-labelled plant image features.

The TSVM is defined as the optimization problem shown below.

$$\min_{y^*, w, b, \xi, \xi^*} \frac{1}{2} \|w\|^2 + C \sum_{i=1}^n \xi_i + C^* \sum_{j=1}^k \xi_j^* \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Subjected to } y_i((w \cdot x_i) + b) \geq 1 - \xi_i \quad i = 1, \dots, n$$

$$y_j((w \cdot x_j) + b) \geq 1 - \xi_j^* \quad j = 1, \dots, k$$

$$\xi_i \geq 0, \quad i=1, \dots, n$$

$$\xi_j^* \geq 0, \quad j=1, \dots, k$$

The TSVM training procedure solves this optimization challenge. The training algorithm has the following step headers.

1. Set parameter C and C*
2. Utilize inductive SVM on training data to obtain initial classifier
3. Determine the number of samples with a positive label based on rule
4. Compute decision function values for all unlabelled samples
5. Label samples with the highest decision function as positive
6. Set temporary effect factor C*
7. Retrain the support vector machine over entire samples
8. Switch labels of one pair of different-labelled unlabelled samples using certain rule to make the value of objective function by using (5)
9. Repeat the process until no pair of samples satisfying the switching condition
10. Increase the value of C* then move to step tmp
11. If (C* > C*) tmp
12. Stop
13. Obtain the output

During the testing phase, the data is compared to the training data, and the kind of plant disease is effectively predicted. Furthermore, the needed water content level for the specific species of plant is predicted using the LDA approach based on the characteristics retrieved from the soil photos.

D. Prediction of Cause for Plant Disease: -

The texture and colour properties of soil photographs are retrieved for predicting the causes of plant leaf diseases. Contrast, intensity, and correlation are textural characteristics. Hue, saturation, and value, or RGB colour spaces, are the colour characteristics. The LDA is used to model the properties of soil photographs with descriptions of plant illnesses, hence measuring the likelihood of soil and plant traits.

In a plant species dictionary, for each picture indexed by m {1, ..., M}:

1. Select K-dimensional topic weight vector θ_m from Dirichlet distribution,

$$p(\theta|\alpha) = \text{Dirichlet}(\alpha)$$
2. For every patch indexed by $n \in \{1, \dots, N\}$ in the image:
3. Select an object category $z_n \in \{1, \dots, K\}$ from the multinomial distribution,

$$p(z_n = k|\theta_m) = \theta_m^k$$
4. Given the selected object category z_n , draw a codeword x from the probability p

$$(x_n = i | z_n = j, \beta) = \beta_{ij}$$

The estimated probability values are sent into the ANN classifier, which predicts whether or not the soil properties are sources of plant illnesses. To train the ANN, the probability values are provided. ANN is composed of three layers: input, hidden, and output. $(x) = x$ are given to the layer of input of neurons. The hidden layer of ANN is defined as tan- sigmoid transfer function.

$$f(x) = \frac{2}{1+e^{-2x}} - 1 \quad (6)$$

The following equation describes the output layer of an ANN.

$$y = f(\sum_{i=1}^n w_i x_i + b) \quad (7)$$

In the preceding equation (6), y denotes the output neuron value; $f(x)$ is the transfer function; w_i denotes the weight values; x_i denotes the input data values; and b denotes the bias value. The soil properties that induce that plant illness are represented by the output neuron value

4. IMAGE ACQUISITION

To train sophisticated visualisation and classification algorithms, a large amount of data is necessary. In general, machine learning and deep learning systems perform better when trained on vast volumes of data. We utilised the Plant Village database implementation.

Figure 1: Block diagram for the hybrid approach detection of plant leaf disease

This "data set" contains 54,323 photos of 14 plants separated into 38 groups of healthy leaves of plants with various sorts of illnesses. This study employed 37,315 photos of five different plant species: apple (7,771 images), maize (7,316 images), potato (3,763 images), tomato (18,345 images), and rice (120 images).

The PlantVillage data set was used to gather plant leaf pictures Preprocessing, feature extraction, feature selection, and classification are all possible with this method. Tables 1– 5 present data-set examples of several leaf diseases in apple, maize, Plants for potatoes, tomatoes, and rice, respectively.

1. Data Augmentation: -
This implies that the model's training must have made it possible for it to learn primary characteristics of a data collection. The following are required for this:
 - i. Data Space: -
The learning data space encompasses the whole spectrum of possibilities, containing the greatest number of possible instances relating to the context of the model's application.
 - ii. Features Space: -
The training data's feature space It also encompasses the range of possibilities, containing the largest number of representations of each data aspect imaginable.
2. To meet the first criteria, we must gather as many training pictures as possible that relate to the context of usage and the goal of our model. To meet the second condition, we must apply data augmentation techniques to the available training pictures, the most frequent of which are affine transformations (horizontal and/or vertical flip, rotation).
2. Deep Features Extraction Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are a kind of neural network that is used to (CNN)
CNNs, as the initials suggest, are a kind of neural network that is best suited for data processing in a network or grid architecture. Images (a network of x and y pixels) are the most common types of data used in this type of network, but time series (data in 1-D with an additional dimension such as a time measurement) and three-dimensional data such as a scanner (two measurements associated with a 1-D image, most of which are associated with the evolution of video in time) are also used .

- 2.1. Convolution Operation: -
"The convolution is an operation that is applied to two functions that use real numbers as arguments."

The operation of convolution is defined mathematically as follows:

$$s(t) = \int x(a)w(t - a)da. \quad (1)$$

The convolution operation is commonly denoted as,

Table 1. Apple plant leaf with disease (source: Plant Village data set [27])

Healthy apple leaf Apple leaf with scab disease

Apple leaf with black rot disease Apple leaf with cedar apple rust disease

Table 2: Corn plant leaf with disease (source: Plant Village data set [27]).

Healthy corn leaf

Corn leaf with common rust disease

Corn leaf with northern leaf blight disease

Corn leaf with cercospora leafspot/grey leaf spot Disease

3: Potato plant leaf with disease (source: Plant Village data set [27]).

Healthy leaf Leaf with late blight disease

$$s(t) = (x * w)(t) \quad (2)$$

The first is referred to as a convolutional neural network in convolutional neural network nomenclature. The first parameter (in this example (x)) is commonly referred to as the input to a stable operation, while the second argument (w in our case) is referred to as the kernel. The output or outcome of this rotation is referred to as the map of features

When dealing with a computer, discrete data can be utilised, thus the integral functions of logical functions must be translated into a number of continuous "discrete" functions as follows:

Table 4: Tomato plant leaf with disease (source: PlantVillage data set [27]).

- (a) Healthy tomato leaf
- (b) “Tomato leaf with bacterial spot disease”
- (c) “Tomato leaf with early blight disease”
- (d) “Tomato leaf with late blight disease”
- (e) “Tomato leaf with mold disease”
- (f) “Tomato leaf with septoria leaf spot disease”
- (g) “Tomato leaf with two-spotted spider mite disease”
- (h) “Tomato leaf with target spot disease”
- (i) “Tomato leaf with mosaic virus disease”
- (j) “Tomato yellow leaf curl virus disease”
- (k) Table 5: Rice plant leaf with disease (source: PlantVillage data set [20]).

Rice leaf with le...
 Rice leaf with brown spot diseases
 Rice leaf with bacterial leaf blight disease

Figure 2: Typical deep convolutional neural network architecture [6].

$$S(t) = (x * w)(t) = \sum_{a=-\infty}^{\infty} x(a)w(t - a). \quad (3)$$

In deep learning applications, the input is often a multidimensional vector (tensor), and the learning algorithm's changed kernel is typically a multidimensional parameter vector.

When picture I is utilised as input, for example, a two-dimensional kernel represented by K is frequently employed.

$$S(i, j) = (I * K)(i, j) = \sum_m \sum_n I(i - m, j - n)K(m, n) \quad (4)$$

In practise, discrete convolutions may be thought of as matrix multiplication:

Figure 3 shows how the 2D input I remains the kernel of K, which is itself a 2D array, and advances along input I executing element-wise multiplication and addition operations. Obtain the convolution result (I K).

Comparative Analysis:

Plant Name	Method	Method used
Tomato Plant	“Optimizing retrained convolutional neural networks for tomato leaf disease detection.”	Tomato plant leaf disease detection from PlantVillage database using CNN
Potato Plant	Plant leaf disease detection using ensemble classification and feature extraction.	Bell pepper, potato, and tomato plant leaf disease detection from PlantVillage database using LBP, GLCM, SIFT, and Gabor features with ensemble classifier
Rice Plant	Detection of rice plant diseases based on deep transfer learning.	Rice plant leaf disease detection from Plant Village database using dense net pretrained on ImageNet
Apple Plant	deep learning in apple leaf disease recognition	Apple leaf disease detection from PlantVillage database using DenseNet-121 deep convolution network
Corn Plant	“A hybrid approach for plant leaf disease detection and classification using digital image processing methods,”	Various plants leaf disease detection from PlantVillage database using GLCM, complex Gabor filter, curvelet, and image moments features with neuro-fuzzy logic classifier

5. CONCLUSION: -

Despite this challenge, it is emphasised that approaching the problem as a binary classification task can facilitate the use and adaptation of the model proposed here for other contexts, reducing the burden on human specialists in annotating examples, which can be particularly useful with other plant images of interest and various types of diseases that may affect them. The purpose of this research is to demonstrate

CNNs' technical capacity in identifying plant illnesses, paving the road for artificial intelligence solutions for farmers. 'It can be especially valuable in the practical setting of agriculture, where many such assessments must be carried out in the field. The Bayesian optimal support vector machine and hybrid feature-based random forest classifier were employed with a collection of colour and texture feature extractors to compare the findings of the convolutional neural network. We have also added the comparative Analysis to define the difference between methods and their results and diseases.

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